

Advocacy Activities of Environmental Non-Governmental Organizations in the Protection of Coastal Areas

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Abstract

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The degradation of coastal areas, which encompass numerous ecological, economic, social, and cultural values, has been increasing in recent years. Deterioration of coastal regions, caused by factors such as urbanization, housing, agriculture, tourism, and climate change, is being countered through effective legal and political efforts. One of the strong actors engaged in this struggle is Non-governmental Organizations (NGOs). Advocacy activities are a crucial tool for environmental NGOs that aim to preserve natural assets like forests, marine, and coastal areas. Advocacy, characterized by robust activism and engagement, holds significant importance in the preservation of coastal areas. In this context, this study aims to elucidate the impact of environmental NGOs in advocacy efforts dedicated to safeguarding one of Turkey's most sensitive ecosystems, the coastlines. The study also seeks to determine which advocacy mechanisms these environmental NGOs utilize most effectively. The research involved an analysis of various sources, including newspaper articles, NGO websites, social media accounts, activity reports, press releases, and publications. Following this research, the advocacy activities conducted by NGOs in Turkey have been categorized, and the obtained findings have been presented in the study enriched with examples. The findings of the study indicate that environmental NGOs effectively employ a comprehensive range of advocacy mechanisms to protect coastal ecosystems. Additionally, it was observed that nationally organized environmental NGOs tend to focus more on knowledge-based advocacy approaches, while locally organized NGOs emphasize action-oriented advocacy strategies.

Kıyı Alanlarının Korunmasında Çevreci Sivil Toplum Kuruluşlarının Savunuculuk Faaliyetleri

Özet

Anahtar Kelimeler:

Kıyı alanları,
Sivil Toplum
Kuruluşları,
Savunuculuk,
Kıyı yönetimi

Ekolojik, ekonomik, sosyal ve kültürel olarak birçok değeri içinde barındıran kıyı alanlarının tahribi son yıllarda giderek artmıştır. Kentleşme ve konut, tarım, turizm, iklim değişikliği gibi baskı unsurlarının neden olduğu kıyı alanlarının bozulmasına karşı hukuki ve politik düzlemde etkili mücadeleler verilmektedir. Bu mücadeleyi gerçekleştiren güçlü aktörlerden bir tanesi Sivil Toplum Kuruluşları (STK) dır. Ormanlar, denizel ve kıyı alanları gibi doğal varlıkları korumayı amaçlayan çevreci STK'ların en önemli başarımları araçlarından birisi savunuculuk faaliyetleridir. Güçlü bir aktivizm ve mücadele içeren savunuculuk kıyı alanlarının korunması için son derece önemlidir. Bu bağlamda çalışma Türkiye'de en hassas ekosistemlerden biri olan kıyıların korunması için gerçekleştirilen savunuculuk faaliyetlerinde çevreci STK'ların etkisini ortaya koymayı ve hangi savunuculuk mekanizmalarını daha etkin biçimde kullandıklarını saptamayı amaçlamıştır. Çalışmada savunuculuk stratejisini değerlendirmek için gazete haberleri, STK'ların web siteleri ve sosyal medya hesaplarındaki haberler, faaliyet raporları, basın bültenleri, STK'ların yayınları gibi birçok doküman taranmıştır. Bu tarama sonrasında Türkiye'deki STK'ların yürüttükleri savunuculuk faaliyetleri kategorize edilmiş ve elde edilen saptamalar örneklerle zenginleştirilerek çalışmada sunulmuştur. Çalışmada çevreci STK'ların kıyı ekosistemlerinin korunmasında savunuculuk mekanizmalarını etkin kullandığı belirlenmiştir. Bununla birlikte ulusal düzeyde örgütlenen çevreci STK'ların daha çok bilgi temelli savunuculuk yaklaşımında, yerel düzeyde örgütlenen çevreci STK'ların ise eylem temelli savunuculuk yaklaşımında bulunduğu sonucuna varılmıştır.

INTRODUCTION

Coastlines are open public spaces accessible to everyone. Hosting humans and other living beings for centuries, coastal areas are among the most crucial environmental assets that need to be preserved due to their biological diversity, economic benefits, and the social and cultural values they encompass. However, the establishment of human settlements, especially cities, in proximity to coastlines, coupled with the increasing urban population, intensifies the pressure on urban coastal areas. The escalating impact of climate change, which we are increasingly feeling, further exacerbates the risks on coastlines. Apart from urbanization and population dynamics, various human activities such as agriculture, industry, commerce, and tourism conducted in coastal areas have led to their degradation.

The intense demand for settlement and usage of coastal areas has transformed them into attractive centers for capital. Indeed, at this point, similar to other spatial transformations, there has been a transition from use value to market value in the transformation of coastal areas. This situation stems from the encroachment of neoliberal policies dominant in the late 20th century over these areas. The transformation of coastal areas and lands, made available to capital through the state, stands as one of the most significant factors contributing to the degradation of coastlines. Furthermore, the investments made by capital in pursuit of profit and rent upon seizing these areas have led to the exclusion of the public from this space and the loss of their communal character. However, the Constitution of the Republic of Turkey explicitly states that the priority in utilizing coastlines should be the public benefit. Despite this right being clearly granted to the public in the Constitution, in practice, it has been granted to the owners of capital. The ecological integrity and carrying capacity of coastal areas that have lost their public character are continuously put at risk by permissions granted for urbanization or various economic activities. As long as the symbiotic relationship between the state and capital continues, the destroying of coastal areas will persist. Achieving ecological sustainability through measures such as coastal planning or integrated coastal management seems unlikely to succeed as long as capital remains unchecked.

The defence of coastal and marine areas under significant pressure becomes inevitable in the face of such threats. To accomplish this defence, numerous environmental NGOs are actively engaged in both domestic and international arenas. While the ideological stance of these NGOs influences the methods and approaches, they adopt in their struggle, all environmental NGOs aim to protect the environment through their advocacy activities. Environmental values of significant importance, such as coastal and marine areas, which encompass various ecological and other functions, have always been at the forefront of these environmental NGOs' agendas.

Compared to other NGOs in Turkey, environmental NGOs, which have a relatively low presence, have some that have particularly focused on issues of coastal area degradation. While certain environmental NGOs concentrate on other areas such as combating desertification or opposing energy power plants, some of these efforts also have implications for coastal areas. This situation adds strength to political and legal battles concerning coastal areas.

One of the most significant tools supporting the efforts of environmental NGOs is advocacy activities. These activities encompass a wide array of actions, from knowledge generation to campaigns, protests, and legal battles, and are frequently utilized by these organizations. The fundamental aim of these activities is the preservation or conservation of the relevant natural asset and, ultimately, the attainment of ecological integrity. Moreover, while conducting advocacy, it is also an important objective to inform the public, draw their attention to these deteriorations, and create awareness.

In this context, the subject that the study focuses on is discussing the advocacy activities undertaken by environmental NGOs for the preservation of coastal areas and examining their effectiveness. Considering

that Turkey possesses significant coastal areas and that spatial transformations in favour of capital are accelerating in the country, the struggles of environmental NGOs are increasingly gaining importance. This aspect also serves as another factor enhancing the significance of the study.

When the literature was reviewed, it was observed that there is a limited number of studies regarding coastal areas. These studies mostly focus on topics such as coastal area planning (Çelik, 2015; Alpaslan and Ortaçşme, 2009; Alpaslan, 2009), coastal area management (Erkal, 2015; Demir, 2018; Yontar & Yılmaz, 2013), and land use changes in coastal areas (Onur, 2007; Bayrak et al. 2022). Studies related to the active struggles and activities of NGOs, which are the key actors in these struggles, are very scarce. This study aims to fill this gap in the literature.

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF COASTAL AREAS AND ISSUES ARISING FROM THEIR USE

The preservation of natural areas by humans is an effort to counteract the harm they cause to the environment. A usage that considers ecological principles, maintains a balance between conservation and utilization, and does not disrupt the harmony and equilibrium of nature will undoubtedly avoid causing harm to the environment. However, concrete realities reveal that this ideal is often not upheld. Forests, wetlands, marine areas, and grazing lands, among other natural spaces, are rapidly deteriorating. Coastal areas, one of the most fragile ecosystems, are also being degraded and losing their natural characteristics, similar to other ecosystems. Thus, the conservation, enhancement, and restoration of ecological values in coastal areas emerge as crucial topics within environmental policy and management.

There are two main reasons for preserving and conserving coastal areas. The first of these is the unique value that coastal areas possess in ecological, economic, social, and cultural terms. Coastal areas, possessing an interface between terrestrial and marine realms, exhibit ecological diversity and multiple functions. These interrelated and interacting coastal zones provide habitat for numerous species, with nearly half of these species relying on coastal areas either as their sole habitat or as one of their habitats. The utilization of coastal habitats by fish and certain invertebrates is particularly crucial for population dynamics and fishing productivity (Seitz et al., 2014: 659).

Coastal areas offer essential ecosystem services to humans and life, such as sustaining biodiversity, nutrient cycling, and storage. These services are indispensable for livelihoods. Coastal habitats are required to access resources like food, salt, minerals, and petroleum, as well as construction materials like sand, rock, and limestone, and genetic diversity utilized in medicine and biotechnology (Martinez et al., 2007).

In developing countries, the livelihoods of over 500 million people are dependent on fishing and aquaculture. The loss of biodiversity and ecosystem degradation in coastal areas disproportionately affects impoverished segments of the population who rely on local ecosystem services for their livelihoods (Khera et al., 2015).

Moreover, coastal areas are crucial ecosystems in regulating the climate and combating climate change. Coastal and marine ecosystems such as mangroves, tidal marshes, and seagrasses and sequester more carbon compared to terrestrial forests. The deterioration of these ecosystems can negatively impact the carbon sink capacity of these areas known as "blue carbon sinks" (IUCN, 2017). Additionally, the rise in sea levels due to climate change can lead to direct consequences such as submergence of coastal areas, coastal flooding, coastal erosion, intrusion of saltwater into coastal groundwater, and economic setbacks. Indirect effects can include changes in land use and alterations in ecosystem dynamics along the coast (TEMA, 2019).

Coastal regions also hold significant cultural and historical value. The aesthetic benefits of these areas significantly contribute to a country's tourism potential. Coastal tourism ranks among the leading economic activities in many countries (Khera et al., 2015). In some cases, this signifies the city's economic dependence on tourism, and this dependency continues in the form of mass tourism (Gezici et al., 2010: 768-769). The

resultant high population in coastal cities due to tourism disrupts both ecosystem services and urban facilities.

The second reason for the need for tighter protection of coastal areas stems from the continuous and systematic pressures these regions face, despite their significance. Coastlines can undergo sudden changes due to factors such as earthquakes and tsunamis, as well as gradual alterations caused by natural forces. However, the primary influences on coastal structures and the main causes of coastal degradation are human factors (Avcı, 2017: 118). Coastal areas are vulnerable spaces facing various anthropogenic pressures and threats. These areas are directly impacted by terrestrial pressures such as agriculture, industry, energy production, urbanization, and extensive urban development. They also face risks like pollution, erosion, sedimentation, damage to coastal and marine biodiversity, and the disappearance of coastal aesthetics.

Coastal areas have hosted denser populations since ancient times, serving as the foundation for empires and witnessing numerous wars fought to seize control of these coastal regions. These areas have been the catalyst for increased production and trade, serving as the initial point of exploration (Demir, 2018: 412). The population in coastal areas has always been higher than in the interior. Migration from inland to coastal areas has often led to a significant increase in the number of coastal inhabitants in comparison to other regions. Consequently, in many coastal areas, particularly in the developing world, population density is extremely high. Such dense population exerts significant pressure on coastal ecosystems due to increased resource usage and pollution (Lundin&Linden, 1993: 468). Coastal ecosystems worldwide, including major deltas, are experiencing a net migration. Despite all the risks, this trend is expected to continue in the coming years (Neuman et al., 2015: 2).

It is important to acknowledge that the environmentally detrimental factors caused by humans are interconnected and cannot be strictly separated. For instance, overpopulation in cities and coastal areas leads to a plethora of issues and exacerbates other problems such as global warming and habitat loss. To illustrate, the urban heat island effect in densely populated cities gives rise to various problems such as air pollution, increased emission levels, and heightened energy demand (Nichols et al., 2019: 127). Considering that coastal areas are densely populated settlements, the likelihood of encountering these issues is higher (Nichols et al., 2019).

THE NEED FOR ADVOCACY IN COASTAL AREAS IN TURKEY

The problems experienced in coastal areas have significant effects on coastal settlements in Turkey, just as they do on all coastal cities. The emergence of coastal issues in Turkey, a country surrounded by seas on three sides, dates back to the post-1970s. During this period, rapid urbanization, the relocation of industry outside city centers, changes in people's leisure and entertainment habits, increased demand for holiday residences, tourism, and transportation have led to increased construction along the coasts. Speculative investments and land speculation have also played a significant role in the increase of coastal construction (Keleş, 1989: 39). The degradation of coasts continues to intensify today, with the addition of new problems brought about by climate change to the pressures arising from high population, urbanization, and economic activities.

In Turkey, the principle that the coasts are under the jurisdiction and disposal of the state and open for the benefit of everyone is enshrined in the Turkish Constitution. Internationally, the "Convention for the Protection of the Mediterranean Sea Against Pollution" (Barcelona Convention), signed in 1976, and the "Convention on the Protection of the Black Sea Against Pollution" (Bucharest Convention), signed in 1992, are significant international legal frameworks that Turkey is a party to, concerning coastal and marine areas. In addition, Turkey has the Coastal Law, Law No. 3621, specifically enacted for the coasts. While the Coastal Law serves as the foundation, various organizations have legal authority and responsibility in the planning, preservation, utilization, and management of coastal areas in Turkey. Coordination and

communication deficiencies among these institutions lead to challenges in the preservation, use, and oversight of coastal areas. Additionally, conflicts between the different legal regulations to which these institutions are subject can result in decisions that may harm coastal areas. These regulations not only lack cohesion but often contain provisions that undermine or render each other ineffective. Furthermore, prolonged dispute processes among these organizations and their inability to prevent unlawful practices render them ineffective at times (Özyurt, 2012: 25). In such cases, the ineffectiveness of these institutions and, in some instances, the legislation itself, underscores the role of NGOs and their advocacy efforts in safeguarding coastal areas.

This multi-faceted administrative structure, contributing to the progressive deterioration of the coastal areas, has resulted in the utilization of this area for individual gain. Social groups, each striving to serve their own interests on the coast, directly or indirectly contribute to the degradation of the coastal quality. Numerous social groups, including entrepreneurs involved in industry or tourism, real estate agents, property developers, laborers migrating from rural areas to work in tourist facilities, and both local and foreign tourists, impact this process. The state is also a part of this process. The state employs these areas as spaces for its own services and positions itself as a regulator and planner in coastal areas (Duru, 2003: 18-19). The desire of capital to appropriate the rent and value of coastal areas, combined with the state's role as the sole regulator of these areas, establishes a relationship between the state and capital. The state and capital jointly act and undertake transformations through different roles. The state's role in spatial transformation is to act in favour of capital, facilitate the necessary conditions for capital, and mediate when required. The tools employed by the state in this process include urban plans, allocations, projects, and incentives. In the transformation of these areas, offered to capital through the state and losing their public characteristics, it also becomes the state's responsibility to secure public consent (Yazar, 2017). However, there is significant opposition to this collaboration. Environmental NGOs are the primary stakeholder in this opposition. NGOs, sometimes align with local administrations, take a stance against the central administration, which is often pro-capital. At times, these NGOs also oppose the actions and activities of local administrations. The differentiation in the relationship between local administrations and environmental NGOs stems from the fact that some local administrations prioritize ecology, while others focus on the economy. While the central administration typically follows a uniform approach, local administrations may have varying perspectives. Therefore, the attitudes of local administrations in coastal areas toward nature conservation are crucial in the context of coastal preservation. Nonetheless, in all cases, environmental NGOs have undertaken the advocacy of these areas not adequately protected by the state. In this context, the mechanisms through which NGOs carry out these advocacy activities will be explained.

MECHANISMS FOR ADVOCACY ACTIVITIES OF NON-GOVERNMENTAL ORGANIZATIONS

In the modern era, civil society, emerging as a separate entity from the state, is considered an indispensable element for a democratic society. Its most fundamental characteristic is its absence from the sway and control of political power and governance, but this position does not imply stepping beyond the boundaries of the law. In other words, civil society operates within the confines and standards set by the law, yet remains outside the authority of political power (Tağma, 2001: 61). Through their activities, NGOs apply pressure and oversight on state institutions, facilitating the limitation of state power and enabling society to control authority. They contribute to the development of democratic values and create avenues for the participation of many sectors that are otherwise excluded from politics (Yılmaz, 2003: 323-324). Civil society supports members in coming together freely and voluntarily to articulate their goals and objectives.

Governments, employing various forms of power, activate regulatory policy tools and pressure mechanisms, while the business sector can exert influence through tools such as attracting investment, paying taxes, or providing employment by putting pressure on the government. Civil society, with non-governmental organizations (NGOs) as a key component, possesses a softer approach for influencing and exerting power

over other actors. Through tools like knowledge production, protests, lobbying activities, and field activism, civil society endeavours to influence decision-makers. It can impact the design or implementation of policies and even collaborate with local governments to assist in the implementation of local policies (Pachego-Vega and Murdie, 2020: 84, as cited in Keck and Sicking, 1998).

Advocacy can be defined as the act of NGOs influencing decision-makers and public policy towards a common interest using various tools and methods, advocating for the representation of vulnerable groups (Aksakoğlu, 2006). NGOs play a significant role as platforms for expressing the needs, demands, and opinions of underrepresented groups. They work to defend the rights of these segments, striving for justice and supporting the principle of equality. They may criticize the government for the sake of better formulating social and other policies or provide services aimed at monitoring (Kalkınma Bakanlığı, 2018: 7). When advocacy is carried out in an organized and structured manner, the likelihood of achieving concrete results increases. Elements such as lobbying and campaigning are part of this process and constitute integral components of advocacy efforts for the protection and enhancement of rights (Tolotto & Silina, 2018: 4).

In conducting advocacy activities, organizations can adopt various approaches that suit their objectives. While some focus on advocating for the prevention of environmental degradation or the mitigation of climate change for the general public interest, others emphasize activities that center on disadvantaged individuals (Aksakoğlu, 2006).

During advocacy efforts, NGOs employ important strategies and tactics to achieve their goals. The advocacy strategies adopted by NGOs can range from collaborating with actors to shaming or blaming actors, encompassing a wide spectrum of approaches. Strategies based on collaboration include activities such as education and research to better inform policymakers, as well as promoting and encouraging alternative policies. Among more aggressive strategies, there are methods such as exerting public pressure (accusation and shaming), resorting to legal action, and filing appeals (Brown et al., 2012). Creating public pressure by engaging in actions that shame and blame the targeted actors is an essential advocacy strategy for NGOs. Mainstream media as well as social media are frequently utilized for shaming actions (Merry, 2013). Shaming or blaming activities can pertain to the environmentally harmful actions undertaken by the targeted actors, as well as their failure to respond to such actions, their reluctance to take responsibility for the damage caused, or their dissemination of misinformation to the public.

Collaborating with local administrations in seeking joint solutions while advocating for the protection of crucial areas by environmental organizations can be effective in resolving local issues. For example, it is also a part of advocacy for NGOs to provide education to the public or support such initiatives to raise awareness or promote understanding on a specific topic (Aksakoğlu, 2006).

Another tool in the struggle for environmental protection and the execution of advocacy efforts is the law. Lawsuits are often initiated against projects or practices believed to be harmful to the environment, and legal battles sometimes extend beyond the borders of Turkey. For example, in the Bergama resistance, the villagers' fight and struggles transcended local boundaries, and they took their legal battles to the European Court of Human Rights (ECHR). The decisions made by the ECHR against Turkey led capitalists and politicians to consider advocacy efforts. However, this awareness has not significantly contributed to environmental protection; instead, it has led to a continuous process of softening and flexing legislation, undermining the effectiveness of law as a means of environmental preservation. Since the 1990s, with the inclusion of the state's repressive apparatus, advocacy practices in favour of capital have been weakened over time (Altıparmak, 2014: 29).

In strengthening local advocacy efforts, international advocacy networks also play a significant role. The involvement of these networks as a pressure mechanism can occur when a state accepts international legal regulations but fails to implement or internalize them. In such cases, transnational actors collaborate with

grassroots NGOs to establish advocacy networks, creating pressure mechanisms (Bal, 2021: 112-113). For instance, in the struggle against the nuclear power plant in Akkuyu, an international network was formed with the arrival of the first Greenpeace ship. Subsequently, scientists, artists, and activists from various countries joined this advocacy network. These groups mainly aimed to carry out advocacy activities by generating technical and scientific knowledge (Kadirbeyođlu, 2005: 107).

RESEARCH METHOD

The study focuses on the advocacy activities of environmental NGOs regarding coastal areas in Turkey. These organizations present their activities to the public through various documents or platforms. Therefore, utilizing document analysis method will provide insights into the activities of these organizations without the need for interviews or observations (Yıldırım&Şimşek, 2008:188). In this context, the study involved the scanning of documents such as scientific reports, press releases, policy and information briefs, activity reports from NGOs, as well as newspaper articles and publications from other institutions. Following this scanning process, advocacy activities carried out by NGOs in Turkey related to coastal areas were categorized, and the findings were presented in the study with enriched examples.

Within the scope of the study, many NGOs specifically engaged in coastal-related work were examined. Some environmental NGOs focus on specific themes such as oceans, climate change, while others address environmental issues in a more integrated and comprehensive manner. Within the coastal context, certain environmental NGOs concentrate solely on marine and coastal areas, while it is evident that NGOs concerned with broader environmental policies and issues also address problems in coastal areas. For instance, the Turkish Foundation for Combating Soil Erosion, Reforestation, and the Protection of Natural Habitats (TEMA) conducts local and national level initiatives concerning various environmental issues such as land use, climate change, and erosion. On the other hand, Turkish Marine Environment Protection Association (TURMEPA) is specifically focused on advocating for and protecting coastal and marine areas. Apart from these, organizations like the Doga, SAD-AFAG (Underwater Research Association - Mediterranean Seal Research Group), Turkish Marine Research Foundation (TÜDAV), Mediterranean Conservation Society, Mediterranean Greens, Antalya Seafaring Platform, Muđla Environmental Platform (MUÇEP), Gökova-Akyaka Lovers Association, Marmaris Ecological Struggle Committee, WWF-Turkey, and many other local and national institutions, organizations, and platforms strive for the conservation of coastal ecosystems. Public institutions like the Union of Chambers of Turkish Engineers and Architects (TMMOB) also contribute to these efforts. However, the study focuses on NGOs, so these public professional organizations are excluded from the scope.

FINDINGS

Following the conducted research, advocacy mechanisms employed by environmental NGOs in Turkey have been categorized and examined as educational and awareness activities, scientific studies and projects, lobbying activities, campaigns, legal actions, and civil actions.

Education and awareness activities

Education and awareness activities conducted in coastal areas aim to help people understand the significance of coastal ecosystems, raise awareness about the conservation of natural resources, and enhance their sensitivity towards potential negative impacts. These activities include a variety of educational programs such as conferences, seminars, workshops, and meetings that cover topics related to the functioning, balance, integrity, functions, issues, and conservation of coastal ecosystems. While these programs are suitable for everyone, their primary target audience is often students and teachers.

When looking at the educational activities of NGOs regarding coastal areas, it can be observed that TURMEPA places a strong emphasis on this topic. With the slogan "Life began in the sea, let it not end in the sea," TURMEPA particularly conducts significant activities against marine and coastal pollution. TURMEPA predominantly engages in advocacy through education and raising awareness. It strives to convey the importance of marine and coastal areas to various segments, especially children, through conferences, educational publications and projects, mainstream and social media shares. Collaborating with schools and other institutions in many cities across Turkey, it aims to instill a sense of nature conservation in children and develops numerous national projects to achieve this awareness. Examples of such projects include the "Mavi Nefes (Blue Breath)" Project, "Benim Hayalim Benim Hikayem (My Dream My Story)" Project, and "Masmavi Deniz Eđitim Kampı (Azure Sea Education Camp)."

One effective approach to raising awareness and conserving coastal areas is through cleanliness campaigns. These activities, often taking place in coastal and shoreline regions, not only help reduce coastal pollution but also draw people's attention to create awareness. For instance, TURMEPA frequently organizes coastal cleaning activities to address waste issues along the shores and deploys waste collection boats in the seas to mitigate waste problems. The collection of coastal waste is carried out by association volunteers.

The informational notes prepared by NGOs for the public also have a significant impact on awareness campaigns. For example, TEMA's "Ekosiyaset Belgesi (Eco-Politics Document)" that they prepare and share with the public is an important source of information for advocacy activities. This document provides insights into TEMA's approaches regarding coastal areas. Apart from eco-politics documents, the Foundation reflects its viewpoints and shares updates on coastal developments in press releases with the public. Additionally, accessing information about coastal developments and the activities of NGOs related to coasts is easily achievable through the activity reports prepared by these organizations.

When it comes to awareness and consciousness-raising efforts, it is observed that NGOs frequently utilize social media in addition to mainstream media. It has been identified that many NGOs have social media accounts and share current information through these platforms. Furthermore, communication tools such as brochures, posters, and booklets are used to highlight the importance and problems of coastal areas.

To gauge public awareness, NGOs sometimes conduct surveys and share the results. For instance, SAD-AFAG has undertaken this approach specifically targeting coasts. The survey asked coastal residents about coastal problems and threats, aiming to draw public attention to these issues (Deniz Haber, 2007). The same NGO conducted a survey targeting professional groups along the Gökova coasts, seeking to identify threats and professional challenges related to the coasts, as well as proposing solutions (SAD-AFAG, 2010).

Scientific research and projects

Scientific data and evidence are essential to understand the functioning and significance of coastal ecosystems and to devise appropriate conservation strategies and advocacy activities. Science and knowledge-based advocacy encourage governments, local authorities, and other stakeholders to take action against issues. They assist in setting priorities for policy development. In essence, scientific research forms the foundation of advocacy efforts. In Turkey, there are significant NGOs conducting scientific studies related to coastal areas. WWF-Turkey is among the leading NGOs in this regard. For example, an association conducting scientific research between Patara and Antalya conveyed the research findings and recommendations for the area to the relevant authority. As a result of the research, it was revealed that the coasts of Kaş are among the richest areas in terms of marine biodiversity, leading to the inclusion of Kaş in the Kekova Special Environmental Protection Area in 2006 (Yokeş, 2020). Another NGO that stands out with its scientific studies is the Doga (Dođa Derneđi). Doga has introduced the "Key Biodiversity Areas" (KBA) methodology in collaboration with an international team of scientists, and the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) has further developed and internationally recognized this methodology as a

standard (Doğa Derneği, n.d.). Using this methodology, the organization's study titled "Key Biodiversity Areas of Turkey" (Doğa Derneği, 2006) demonstrates how these areas can be conserved and defended in the long term and in a comprehensive manner. The effort of an NGO to conduct such work is a valuable endeavour. The study identifies KBAs, provides information about the status, habitat, species, and usage of these areas. Furthermore, it identifies threats to these areas and outlines conservation efforts related to them. Such scientific studies serve as important guides for advocacy and conservation activities. Indeed, this study formed the basis for the "Protection and Defence of Key Biodiversity Areas Along Turkish Coasts " project by SAD-AFAG.

SAD-AFAG is one of the NGOs that has been consistently engaged in scientific work since its establishment. The Middle East Technical University Underwater Society (ODTÜ Sualtı Topluluğu), founded by a group of students and academics in 1985, transitioned to an organized NGO format to achieve its goals more professionally and established SAD-AFAG in 1994 (SAD-AFAG, 2018). An important feature of SAD-AFAG is its specialized research groups. Each research group focuses on specific aspects related to marine and coastal areas, conducting research and carrying out advocacy activities within their respective fields.

One of the scientific research and projects carried out by SAD-AFAG focusing on coastal areas and achieving success is the "Conservation and Defence of Important Nature Areas on the Coasts of Turkey." SAD-AFAG conducted this project between 2015 and 2019, executing a protection and advocacy initiative for 28 at-risk coastal areas defined as Important Nature Areas. Within the scope of the project, correspondence with relevant authorities took place, reports were prepared, all information and documents were shared with the public, and the significance of conserving these areas was communicated to all stakeholders. The aim was to prevent habitat loss in these areas through collaboration among local NGOs, nature conservation platforms, legal experts, and citizens. Additionally, as a result of this project, a legal regulation proposal addressing the issues faced by Mediterranean seals in their habitats was accepted and implemented. Most of the attempts at urbanization in the project areas were halted, but unfortunately, irreversible habitat destruction occurred in some cases (Kıraç&Ververi, 2019: 17-18).

Lobbying

Utilizing lobbying activities is important for the effective and successful execution of advocacy strategies. NGOs that are financially and institutionally strong and experienced have a greater potential to influence relevant institutions. However, the question of whether environmental NGOs in Turkey possess such power is debatable, as this situation can vary based on numerous factors. For instance, NGOs that maintain better relationships with politicians and adopt a moderate stance tend to engage in more powerful lobbying. Public reactions also impact the strength of lobbying efforts.

Considering that a significant portion of environmental NGOs in Turkey organize at the local level, it can be argued that lobbying is relatively weak. Eryılmaz (2018) indicated that environmental NGOs in Turkey are divided into professional lobbying organizations at the central level and volunteer protesters at the local level. Structural changes in NGOs like WWF-Turkey, TEMA, Doga, along with the professionalization of their staff, dependency on funding sources, and avoidance of confrontation with government institutions, have led these NGOs to transform from pressure groups into entities engaged in "Public Interest Lobbying." However, some of these NGOs occasionally engage in struggles against centralized governance, emphasizing their role as pressure groups.

Concerning coastal areas, locally organized NGOs focus on civil and mass actions, while larger professional NGOs prioritize lobbying activities. Through lobbying efforts, numerous projects related to coastal areas have been realized, and legal regulations perceived as detrimental to coastlines have been withdrawn. For instance, TEMA expressed concerns that proposed amendments to the Mining Law would adversely affect

not only forests, agricultural lands, wetlands, and national parks but also coastal areas. Through robust lobbying efforts, TEMA succeeded in having the proposal withdrawn (TEMA, 2013).

Campaigns

Environmental NGOs frequently resort to campaigns, which are among the most essential tools for achieving advocacy strategies. Unlike advocacy, campaigns are not long-term processes. They focus on specific topics within a defined timeframe and target a particular audience. Regarding coastal issues, environmental NGOs organize campaigns to protect coastal ecosystems and marine life, promote clean coasts by addressing waste and pollution, campaign against coastal urbanization, oppose marine pollution or overfishing, and carry out education and awareness campaigns. Collaboration between NGOs can also occur in these campaigns. For instance, in the 1990s, SAD-AFAG conducted a successful campaign in collaboration with local NGOs against the urbanization of Karaada for tourism purposes (Doğa Derneği, 2006: 208).

Signature campaigns, which have become more visible with the influence of social media, are also effectively used for advocacy purposes. Local NGOs, in particular, tend to resort to signature campaigns more frequently. For example, MUÇEP (Mugla Environmental Protection and Tourism Platform) has organized signature campaigns with titles such as "Another Mugla is Possible!", "Let Natural Sites Stay Natural," and "Don't Touch Alavara." Another example is the initiative by the Kaş Culture and Environment Association, which launched a signature campaign against the zoning plan amendment that would open up the coastlines in Kaş for urban development. This signature campaign was successful, leading to the rejection of the zoning plan changes (Yeşil Gazete, 2023).

Legal appeal

Since coastlines are under the jurisdiction and authority of the state, any actions or decisions taken in these areas directly concern the administration. Article 125 of the Constitution of the Republic of Turkey stipulates that legal recourse is available against all actions and decisions of the administration. Therefore, environmental NGOs can sue the administration or be involved in lawsuits for actions or transactions related to coastal areas. Zoning plans or coastal management plans, EIA decisions, decisions regarding the privatization of coastlines, decisions concerning structures on the coast, changes to coastal legislation, and decisions to alter the status of coastal areas are the subjects of legal cases that environmental NGOs bring against the administration in relation to coastlines.

A recent example of legal action against coastal management plans is the case in 2021 where the TEMA Foundation requested the partial annulment and suspension of execution of the Integrated Coastal Area Plans for the provinces of Aydın-Muğla and Balıkesir-Çanakkale (TEMA, n.d.). The legal process is still ongoing. These plans sparked significant public outcry, and citizens, local administrations, and many environmental NGOs raised objections against the plans.

Administrative actions regarding the reduction of the protection status of the coasts also lead environmental NGOs to apply to the judiciary. For instance, in April 2006, the Underwater Research Association, Doga, Ege Doga Derneği, and Greenpeace Mediterranean filed two separate annulment lawsuits against decisions to downgrade the conservation status of protected areas along the coastlines of Alaçatı and Çeşme (Doğa Derneği, 2023).

MUÇEP is highly effective in lawsuits against privatizations. MUÇEP vehemently opposes the privatization of coastlines, advocating for public access to the use of these areas. It combats coastal encroachments, profiteering, and pillaging of coastlines. MUÇEP has stated that it will employ all legitimate means of struggle, including filing lawsuits, for lands in Muğla and other provinces that are being sought to be sold by the Privatization Administration (MUÇEP, 2022a). Indeed, on April 5, 2021, the Platform filed a lawsuit

against the decision that would allow the privatization of Kargı Cove in Datça for the construction of a hotel and parking lot (MUÇEP, 2021a).

Lawsuits against EIA decisions are also crucial for the preservation of coastal areas. MUÇEP's Marmaris Assembly and Marmaris Ecological Struggle Committee filed a lawsuit on July 5, 2022, against the decision stating "Environmental Impact Assessment is not necessary" for an integrated project initiated by a company named Sinpaş, which includes constructions like hotels, timeshare properties, villas, and shopping malls in the İçmeler/Kızılkum area (MUÇEP, 2022b). While an injunction decision was issued following the lawsuit, MUÇEP alleged that the company continued its activities and subsequently reported this to the prosecutor's office (MUÇEP, 2022c).

Civil actions

Advocacy strategies can be more successful when supported by strong actions. Protests, marches, demonstrations, rallies, sit-ins, signature campaigns, press releases are civil actions carried out by local communities and NGOs to protect coastal ecosystems. Additionally, events such as celebrations, festivals, and camps held along coastlines also draw attention to the preservation of coastal ecosystems. For instance, the "Joyful Coasts Festival" held in Datça emphasizes that coastlines belong to the public, and raises a voice against the illegal leasing of the coasts (BirGün, 2023).

These types of actions related to coastlines are predominantly led by local NGOs and conducted at the local level. For example, following an announcement by the MUÇEP Gökova Assembly, many citizens gathered in Akyaka to protest coastal constructions and concluded their demonstration with a press release (MUÇEP, 2021b). In 2021, at the call of Datça Democracy Platform and City Defense, Datça locals and NGOs came together. Even parliament members and political party representatives reportedly participated (MUÇEP, 2021c). In 2022, again upon MUÇEP's call, Datça citizens gathered, marching against the leasing of coasts, asserting "coasts belong to all of us" (MUÇEP, 2022d). In Marmaris, numerous local NGOs engaged in a vigil to prevent a company named Sinpaş from constructing within a national park area due to the company's continuation of construction despite a court ruling (Gazete Duvar, 2022).

One of the widespread actions related to coastal areas is the "towel movement." Originating in Greece, this movement has spread to the Aegean coasts of Turkey. Taking place in various coastal settlements like Foça, Datça, Çeşme, and Altınova, this movement has become a symbol of citizens' fight against the privatization of coasts.

CONCLUSION

In Turkey, a country with an extensive coastline, the pressures of population, urbanization, and economic activities on the coasts began in the 1980s and have continued to increase until today. The commodification and commercialization of many values associated with these areas have led to the pursuit of profits and rents from these areas, prompting capital to focus on them. As a result of the convergence of various pressures, coastal ecosystems, which hold numerous values, are rapidly deteriorating. Biodiversity is diminishing, species are disappearing, and aesthetic beauties are being destroyed. Although some areas have been rehabilitated and restored through conservation and advocacy efforts, irreversible losses have occurred in others. Therefore, the preservation of these areas should be a priority within the environmental agenda.

While the primary responsibility for implementing policies for the conservation of natural assets lies with the state, the symbiotic relationship between the state and capital raises questions about the state's protective role. In such a situation, NGOs, perceived as a third actor apart from the public and private sectors, come into play. Environmental NGOs, which constitute a small proportion of NGOs, have chosen to organize at local and national levels and have developed various advocacy tools to protect the environment.

When it comes to the effectiveness of the tools/mechanisms used by environmental NGOs, it can be said that resorting to the judiciary is one of the mechanisms that operate effectively. Typically, lawsuits related to coasts predominantly revolve around the issue of private property in coastal areas. However, the common goal of the lawsuits filed by NGOs is to serve the public interest. NGOs believe that adopting a rights-based approach advocating open access to coasts for everyone will ensure the realization of the public interest. Furthermore, NGOs view the utilization of coasts as part of the right to environment, promoting people living in a healthy environment. Given the frequent occurrence of violations of public rights in coastal areas, resorting to the judiciary becomes inevitable for NGOs. Since it does not incur very high costs, education and awareness campaigns are on the agenda of every environmental NGO, and with the increase in these efforts, their effectiveness also increases. Scientific research and projects are not effectively used by every NGO. This situation depends on the budget of the environmental NGO and the priorities within that budget. Although lobbying activities have the potential to influence government and institutions significantly, the underdevelopment of this culture often hinders the effective use of lobbying. It can be said that many locally organized environmental NGOs lack the power to engage in lobbying activities. Therefore, if used effectively, lobbying has the potential to be one of the most powerful advocacy mechanisms.

When examining the advocacy activities of environmental NGOs dedicated to preserving the coasts, some differentiations can be observed among these organizations. National-level environmental NGOs tend to focus on education and awareness campaigns, scientific research, projects, and lobbying efforts. They have adopted an information-based advocacy approach and often engage in discussions without necessarily anchoring them in the political sphere. On the other hand, local-level environmental NGOs predominantly engage in civil actions and campaigns, emphasizing a more action-oriented advocacy approach. These organizations prioritize active struggle, organization, and resistance. Legal action is a mechanism frequently employed and trusted by all NGOs. However, the disregard for court decisions at times necessitates on-the-ground activism. In this context, the prominent role of civil actions led by NGOs cannot be underestimated.

In summary, the active roles of NGOs, engaging in both legal and scientific efforts as well as field activities, are indispensable in the conservation of natural assets such as coastal areas. In the endeavour for a sustainable way of life, it is essential to provide support for environmental NGOs to continue their conservation efforts. Whether such support exists in Turkey and the challenges faced by environmental NGOs, such as financial constraints, capacity development gaps, and insufficient public support, could be proposed as a separate subject for investigation and evaluation.

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